

ISic0302

I.Sicily inscription 0302

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Estella Kessler,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

The text is reported as engraved across the epistyles of four columns

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Q(uintus) Lusius

2. Laberius

3. proconsul

4. thermas

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation (en)

Quintus Lusius Laberius, proconsul, (erected?) the baths

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491512

EDR 141067

EDCS 21900337

Bibliography

Gualtherus, G. 1624. Siciliæ obiacentium insular. et Bruttiorum antiquæ tabulæ, cum animadversionib. Messanae. At no.32-35

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7018 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650756>)

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